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Repetita iuvant? Exploring the Evolutionary Meaning of Repetitive Elements in Adaptation and Aging.

Elia Mario Biganzoli^{1,2*} and Valentina Bollati^{3,4*}

¹ *Department of Biomedical and Clinical Sciences (DIBIC), University of Milan, 20157 Milan, Italy.*

² *Data Science Research Center (DSRC), University of Milan, 20157 Milan, Italy*

³ *EPIGET - Epidemiology, Epigenetics and Toxicology Lab, Department of Clinical Sciences and Community Health, University of Milan, 20122 Milan – Italy.*

⁴ *Epidemiology Unit, Fondazione IRCCS Ca' Granda Ospedale Maggiore Policlinico, 20122 Milan – Italy*

*Corresponding Authors

elia.biganzoli@unimi.it

valentina.bollati@unimi.it

Abstract

The traditional understanding of human DNA, dominated by the concept of "selfish DNA," has been challenged by emerging research highlighting the evolutionary significance of non-coding and repetitive elements (REs). This review proposes a paradigm shift towards viewing these elements as crucial to understanding human adaptability and health, particularly in the context of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), which are the leading cause of global mortality. Our hypothesis emphasizes the adaptive role of REs, suggesting their involvement in the dynamic response to environmental changes and stressors, and their contribution to the modulation of health and disease states. This perspective integrates the effects of lifestyle factors and the epidemiological transition from infectious to chronic diseases, underscoring the interconnectedness of human health, environmental influences, and evolutionary biology. We advocate for a social biocentric approach to health and disease, one that recognizes the influence of REs on the development of NCDs and their potential role in maintaining species homeostasis in response to a changing environment. This comprehensive interpretation of genetic and environmental interactions invites a reevaluation of health strategies, moving beyond disease prevention to fostering biologically sustainable behaviors that support global health and ecosystem stability.

Keyword

Non-communicable diseases; Repetitive Elements; Human evolution; Social dynamics; Exposome; Adaptation.

Have you ever asked yourself why 90% of human DNA contains non-coding elements? Have you ever wondered why every cell division requires the copying of thousands and thousands of repetitive elements of unknown function and sequences derived from ancestral viral infections? Have you ever questioned why natural selection did not eliminate such a supposed waste of energy? And lastly, have you ever wondered about the adaptive evolutionary significance of cell senescence, low-grade chronic inflammation, and, finally, chronic diseases?

These questions highlight the need for a new framework to interpret scientific evidence on the evolutionary implications of accelerated aging and age-related diseases in humans. This framework should also include all animal species and possibly plants. This paper aims to present the evidence supporting our hypothesis, offering a new interpretation of findings on the evolutionary role of DNA repetitive elements in the context of species and community homeostasis. These elements impact the dynamics among individuals, populations, and the environment, and play a role in cell senescence, tissue and organ health, and the development of chronic diseases (NCDs).

NCDs are associated with accelerated aging and contribute to the annual demise of 41 million individuals, representing 74% of all global fatalities.^{1,2} Moreover, NCDs are intertwined with the phenomenon of anthropization of our planet.^{3,4} In fact, apart from the accumulation of environmental toxicants, human lifestyles are major determinants of health.⁵ Unsustainable lifestyles, characterized by inadequate physical activity, nutrition, sleep, and associated stress and mental health issues, lead to the accumulation of senescent cells triggering the onset of low-grade chronic inflammation with aging acceleration and the development and progression of NCDs.⁶

The epidemiological transition has been indicated as a major event marking two distinct eras in the health history of the Western world. This transition occurred in the early modern period and is characterized by a shift in disease and mortality patterns from those due to infectious diseases to those due to NCDs.⁷ Recent pandemic phenomena have prompted reflection on the existence of cyclical rather than linear evolutionary processes on the planet. However, it's important to note that disease and mortality resulting from infections and NCDs are not independent processes (e.g. NCDs have been highlighted as important risk factors for COVID-19 mortality⁸).

Investigating NCDs is a pressing priority to safeguard the health of human populations. However, the prevailing approach has largely concentrated on disease prevention by managing risk factors,⁹ rather than actively promoting biologically sustainable behaviors that boost overall health protection.

From a reductionist, anthropocentric perspective, "Health" is often conceptualized as a prototype linked to the stereotypical desire for eternal youth, essentially the absence of aging. Pathologies are either viewed as accidents or inevitable biological defects, possibly associated with the aging process. In this framework, cellular senescence and biological aging are perceived as the gradual deterioration of functional characteristics in living organisms, without recognizing their highly governed biological roles in social and environmental adaptation, as well as long-term evolutionary processes.

In line with this viewpoint, humans strive for biological perfection through cultural evolution. Biomedicine is seen as a means to fight senescence, eliminate diseases, and mitigate their severe consequences, only to achieve maximum individual longevity. Aging and death, in this context, are viewed as a personal failure and medical care is conceptualized as the “repair” of human individuals, embodying an engineered vision of human health. Human brain development and cultural/technological evolution were indeed propelled by the need for self-protection through social care behaviors. However, the anthropocentric perspective may stem from humanity's ancestral frustration of living in a hostile environment and occupying a lower position in the food chain¹⁰ and, in an extremely reductionist view, humans are now turning to artificial life technologies (e.g. AI) to manage health, addressing perceived shortcomings of human biology.

An alternative biocentric view, focused on biodiversity and adaptation rather than solely on frailty, is necessary. This view would transform our understanding of health/disease by adopting sustainable approaches that incorporate sociocultural factors, leading to positive impacts on society.

The challenges posed by environmental changes induced by human activity compel us to rethink the concept of human health in relation to the overall health of the planet. In this context, as someone wrote: “The inflammatory diseases we are seeing today are not the cause of the body's dysfunctional reactions. They are the body's correct responses to a pathological world”.¹¹ Throughout the history of the planet's species, diseases have not been caused by evolutionary defects. Instead, they are adaptive responses developed through evolution to maintain social homeostasis within species in a dynamic environment, prioritizing group fitness over individual fitness.

Each cell of an organism must engage in a continual dialogue with this dynamic world, understanding what actions to take and when.¹² Starting from the awareness of this dialogue, in a healthy organism, every change should be interpreted and translated into systemic, tissue, and cellular processes aimed at facilitating the adaptation of the individual, ultimately maximizing survival chances.¹³ At the same time, the individual is an integral part of a larger community and ecosystem, where individual benefits must not outweigh those of the higher level as a whole.

The intricate layers of encoded information, structures and functions evolve according to cooperative “social” principles. They develop adaptations to the environment within the framework of dynamic homeostasis, propelling the process of evolution forward.¹⁴

From this perspective, the notion of dominant biological elements, such as DNA as the sole source of coded evolving information leading to humans as the dominant species, contradicts the primary social principles governing life evolution on our planet. Instead, humans should feel the deep biosocial responsibility of their cultural/technological evolution in preserving and promoting the entire life heritage of the planet, as this is the only path to survival.

The hypothesis: Repeating Elements as transducers of biological adaptability

The concept of "selfish DNA", introduced by British biologist Richard Dawkins in his book "The Selfish Gene", originated as a term used to describe certain genetic elements within an organism's genome that appeared to serve no direct purpose for the host organism's survival or reproduction.¹⁵ These elements seemed to exist solely to replicate themselves and increase their presence within the genome, often at the expense of the organism's overall fitness.¹⁶ In the context of "selfish DNA", repetitive elements in the genome have often been considered prime examples: transposons and retrotransposons are sequences of DNA that can duplicate and insert themselves in various locations within an organism's genome.¹⁷ Their behavior resembles that of a genetic parasite, as they proliferate without necessarily providing any immediate benefit to the host organism.

However, our understanding of repetitive elements within the genome has undergone a profound transformation, resulting in a complete redefinition of their significance and role. We now recognize they can exert influence on gene regulation, drive evolution, and even contribute to the diversity and adaptability of species.¹⁸

It is now worth to consider the potential redefinition of the role of these genetic elements, moving away from the term "selfish DNA" towards "cooperative DNA". This reframing acknowledges their dynamic nature and the mutually beneficial functions they perform within the genome.

According to our hypothesis, repetitive transposable elements (REs) are key to understanding human (and other species) biological adaptability to the dynamic world in which each individual lives, often referred to as the "exposome".¹⁹ Historically, REs have been labeled as "junk DNA".²⁰ Despite only constituting 1-2% of the human genome, protein-encoding genes are often perceived as having greater functional significance, leading us to attribute total value to them. However, REs are actively retained in the genome, albeit epigenetically silenced by mechanisms such as DNA methylation, which suppresses their expression/mobility and maintains genomic stability.²¹ The dynamic properties of REs likely confer upon them the advantage of evolving in response to environmental changes and evolutionary pressures.²²

REs can be categorized into two groups based on the presence or absence of long terminal repeats (LTRs). Non-LTR elements include short interspersed nuclear elements (SINEs, e.g., Alu) and long interspersed nuclear elements (LINEs).²³ The majority of LTR elements are derived from human endogenous retroviruses and represent about 8% of the human genome.²⁴ Increasing evidence indicates that REs are frequently hypomethylated in various human pathologies, including cancer,²⁵ cardiovascular²⁶ and respiratory diseases,²⁷ and psychiatric disorders.²⁸ However, the high proportion of these sequences in our genome and their responsiveness to various stimuli underscores the need for a paradigm shift in interpreting current scientific evidence to understand the functions of REs and their potential links to disease development.²¹

RE methylation has indeed been demonstrated to be actively modulated in response to environmental triggers which encompass a wide range of factors including air pollutants,^{29,30} viral

infections,³¹ physical exercise,³² early violence,³³ etc., leading to hypomethylation of the REs. Much of the available data has focused on assessing the methylation levels of Alu and LINE-1 elements, which provide insights into the global methylation status across various subfamilies.²⁹ Therefore, the initial premise of our hypothesis posits that the modulation of RE methylation serves as a pivotal mechanism for explaining human adaptability to the exposome, encompassing the myriad triggers experienced throughout an individual's life course.

To make an analogy that explains the functioning of REs according to our view, we can think of how a computer programming language works (Figure 1).

The path from a programmer's input to a machine's instructions involves steps to simplify the complex original message. High-level programming languages are easy for programmers but far from computer language. Similarly, the exposome provides complex inputs that must be simplified for cells to translate into biological processes. Just as machine language is binary and understandable by computers to give rise to executable programs, cells are activated (i.e., biological processes are turned on/off) by simplified messages summarizing a multitude of complex inputs (exposome). Assembly language, which translates text into machine instructions, parallels the biological activation (hypomethylation) of REs in our hypothesis.

Figure 1

Figure 1: Turning a complex message into a simple message.

The hypomethylation of REs leads to an increase in RE transcripts as a primary consequence, along with reduced chromatin stability.³⁴ As REs are produced, they have the potential to insert into proteins or regulatory regions of coding genes.³⁵ In some cases, these insertions may cause diseases by disrupting gene functions. Furthermore, even if the insertion of a RE sequence does not directly impact gene functioning, it can still influence the amount of mRNA produced from that gene.³⁶ Studies have shown that weakly expressed genes tend to contain more RE sequences on average

compared to strongly expressed genes.³⁷ Additionally, REs can give rise to new forms of coding regions, and some of these may confer new abilities to individuals, selected through environmental pressures and fixed in evolution.²²

It is intriguing that REs have been maintained for hundreds of million years, rather than being negatively selected, and have played a significant role in shaping the evolution of the genomes where they reside. Moreover, the mutation rate of REs can be used to estimate when they were generated in evolution.³⁸ Looking to the history of Earth, we highlight the association with major events leading to species adaptation (Figure 2). For instance, focusing on Alu elements, it is well-established that the majority of them were successfully integrated in the human genome approximately 34-35 million years ago,³⁹ coinciding with a drop in carbon dioxide levels that led to Earth entering a period of global cooling known as an icehouse state.⁴⁰ Furthermore, examining the development of different subfamilies of Alu elements reveals correlations with various climatic changes throughout history. For example, the development of AluSx and AluJ⁴¹ coincides with a sudden global warming event 55 million years ago,⁴² while the emergence of AluY⁴¹ corresponds to a climate change event 25 million years ago characterized by cooler and drier conditions. Similarly, the development of AluYa5 and AluYb8 aligns with a period of slow, continuous cooling that occurred around 15 million years ago.⁴³

Figure 2

Figure 2: Hypothesized Association between the Integration of Alu Elements in the Human Genome and Major Climatic Events in Earth's History.

It may be assumed that REs are contributing biological entities in social organisms evolving as communities of different species, typically maintained at a level that does not generate serious instabilities in the genome but is capable of generating meaningful variability in response to

evolutionarily significant environmental pressures as well as short-term adaptive needs. They are likely the major source of resilience of metazoans.

Imagine an explorer carrying a backpack filled with various tools. Some of these tools may seem unnecessary or even cumbersome, weighing the explorer down without apparent use. For instance, the explorer might carry a flare gun that remains unused for months, adding to the weight of the backpack. One day the explorer finds himself in a life-threatening situation: he is lost, the night is quickly approaching and he fires the flare gun into the sky, signaling for help, ultimately saving his life.

Similarly, REs are like these tools. They might seem superfluous or even harmful, contributing to genetic load without immediate benefit. However, under certain environmental pressures or challenges, an RE might activate a variation that provides a crucial advantage, allowing the organism to survive and adapt in a way that would not have been possible otherwise.

Indeed, while REs play a crucial role in driving adaptation at the species level, there is a price to pay for the individual.⁴⁴ Extreme adaptation capability in heterogeneous environments (e.g. humans), is characterized by the accumulation of numerous REs in the genome with potential large-scale genomic disturbances.

Therefore, the second part of our hypothesis suggests that over-adaptation capability of individuals driven by REs may potentially disrupt the global homeostasis of their species. To put it another way, individuals have the capacity to adapt in response to stimuli, which can shape REs and aid in adaptation. However, the social adaptation of species communities needs to avoid individual unsustainable behaviors (for instance, a high-calorie diet coupled with low physical activity leading to inefficient energy utilization and resource mismanagement). Thus, REs should also serve as a mechanism for the biosocial control: as said above “responses fixed in the evolution of the species to support the social homeostasis of the species themselves in response to a dynamic world”.¹¹ Therefore, they may act as regulators to ensure the overall balance and well-being of the species in the face of environmental challenges and individual behaviors that may be detrimental to the ecosystem or planetary health.

These evidences indicate that the principle of optimality (fitness) in living organisms is governed by dynamic potential, rather than a static cross-sectional perspective, reflecting their ability to adapt to changing environments.

Cancer as a coherent example

Cancer biology might serve as a compelling example of how chronic disease can be seen as adaptation to the environment for species' social homeostasis.⁴⁵ Various species exhibit diverse cancer occurrence conditions, providing a clear indication that the phenomenon cannot solely be attributed to chance or to the biological "wear and tear" of individuals (accumulation of mutations in accordance with the Somatic Mutation Theory, SMT).⁴⁶ The existence of different average cancer

rates among species, in fact, suggests that there are underlying factors influencing cancer development beyond random mutations or natural aging processes. This indicates a potential role for environmental and evolutionary pressures in shaping cancer susceptibility and prevalence across different species. Therefore, understanding cancer biology in the context of species-specific adaptations and environmental interactions can provide valuable insights into the broader dynamics of species' social homeostasis and disease regulation.

Peto's paradox, which contradicts the SMT, suggests that animals with larger body masses and cellularity do not necessarily exhibit a higher risk of cancer.⁴⁷ This observation raises intriguing questions about the spread of cancer across species in relation to the hypothesis of their social adaptation to the environment. For example, certain animals like elephants increased the number of copies of the P53 gene, mitigating the impact of cancer on their mortality.⁴⁸ Generally, these adaptations are more prevalent in species subjected to less social or environmental competition. Stable and less competitive environments, like pelagic ones, are characterized by the presence of species with higher body masses and greater longevity.⁴⁹ Additionally, species with adaptations for environmental resistance to predation and abundant food reserves, such as turtles, often exhibit long lifespans. In such conditions, cancer may not confer a biological advantage to species' homeostasis and may have either been eradicated or never existed in the evolutionary history of that species.

However, where one might expect cancer to play a significant role in social or global homeostasis as a chronic pathology remains a relevant question. It may be beneficial to develop an alternative perspective that moves away from viewing individuals as structurally homogeneous entities.

Individuals are composed of a series of biological processes integrated through evolution in response to external or internal environmental stimuli. The integration of these processes represents a continuous modulation of homeostasis as a dynamic condition linked to individual history, social interactions, species dynamics, and interactions with other species in competition or cooperation.

In this perspective, cancer can be seen as a biological process competitive for individual existence but potentially functional for the restoration of homeostasis at higher levels of biosocial organization. Homeostasis, being dynamic, assumes a "fractal" condition reproduced at different levels of the involved biological systems, such as molecules, cells, tissues, organs, individuals, communities, etc.

It's important to recognize that humans do not represent the highest level of biological systems involved, and their cultural and technological evolution must grapple with the imperative of global sustainability. Therefore, understanding cancer within the broader context of dynamic homeostasis across different levels of biological organization can provide valuable insights into the complexities of health, disease, and sustainability at both individual and global scales.

Indeed, cancer, as a chronic pathology, can be viewed as an endoparasite that emerges when infectious causes determined by exoparasites are no longer prevalent, as seen during the

epidemiological transition. Its impact becomes more pronounced in advanced ages, emerging as a primary cause of mortality in Western human populations.

What factors accelerate cancer mortality? Conditions such as the accumulation of energy reserves (adiposity) and/or their underutilization (sedentarism) are significant contributors. For this fundamental reason, there is a strong rationale for the effectiveness of a calorie-restricted diet and aerobic physical exercise (particularly walking) in health protection, as they generally help prevent chronic diseases, including cancer.

Energy metabolism and adaptation. The linking role of REs

Throughout the Paleolithic era spanning millions of years, humans adapted their biology to a lifestyle characterized by continuous movement for feeding and survival, which required maintaining a specific energy balance.⁵⁰

The transition from hunter-gatherer societies to the settled communities of the Neolithic period occurred relatively rapidly, taking approximately 10,000 years.⁵¹ Despite these significant societal changes, the rapid pace of this transition did not allow the metabolic demands to adapt accordingly. Thus, the fundamental biological necessity for maintaining a specific energy balance has remained unchanged.

In modern sedentary individuals, this mismatch between our biological imprinting and current lifestyle can lead to mitochondrial dysfunction with increased leakage of electrons from the electron transport chain during cellular respiration. This leakage, together with chronic inflammation, can generate reactive oxygen species (ROS).⁵² Sedentary lifestyles may also correlate with other unhealthy habits, such as poor diet (low in antioxidants), which can increase ROS production.⁵³ ROS cause significant damage to cellular components, including DNA, proteins, and lipids.⁵⁴

Glutathione (GSH), a major antioxidant within cells, plays a crucial role in neutralizing ROS and maintaining cellular redox balance.⁵⁵ Elevated ROS levels can deplete glutathione, impairing the cell's antioxidant defense and leading to oxidative stress.⁵⁶ This stress can alter the activity of DNA methyltransferases, the enzymes responsible for adding methyl groups to DNA, as they contain redox-sensitive cysteine residues which can be modified by ROS, lowering the enzyme activity and thereby impacting DNA methylation.⁵⁷ Moreover, when ROS stimulate the synthesis of glutathione, the metabolic demand for glutathione precursors, including cysteine, increases.⁵⁸ The synthesis of glutathione involves the consumption of homocysteine, which is produced from S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) during the methylation cycle. As the demand for glutathione increases due to ROS-induced oxidative stress, more homocysteine is consumed to produce cysteine for glutathione synthesis, depleting the availability of homocysteine for remethylation back to methionine, which in turn reduces the regeneration of SAM.⁵⁹ Consequently, reduced levels of SAM may impair DNA methylation and other methylation-dependent processes, as SAM is a critical methyl donor.⁵⁹ Thus, the increased synthesis of glutathione in response to ROS can lead to

decreased SAM levels, potentially affecting methylation reactions and overall cellular function (Figure 3).⁶⁰ If the cell experiences an impairment in methylation processes, it will tend to prioritize essential gene regulation, often at the expense of methylating REs, leading to hypomethylation of these regions.⁶¹

Figure 3

Figure 3: The balance between Glutathione Synthesis and DNA Methylation, which highlights the trade-off between the need to counteract oxidative stress through increased glutathione synthesis and the potential impact on DNA methylation processes.

Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate (NADPH), primarily produced by the Pentose Phosphate Pathway, is closely linked to glutathione biology and crucial for cellular redox homeostasis.⁶² NADPH maintains the pool of reduced glutathione (GSH) by providing the reducing power necessary for the conversion of oxidized glutathione (GSSG) back to GSH, thus enabling glutathione to continue its role in neutralizing harmful oxidative species within the cell.⁶² NADPH increases the expression of sirtuins,⁶³ which are a group of enzymes able to impact glucose and lipid metabolism, mitochondrial function, and overall energy homeostasis. Interestingly, Sirtuins (SIRT 1-7) have been linked to lifespan extension in various organisms⁶⁴ since their early origin in evolution. SIRT6 maintains a heterochromatin state of a wide range of genetic elements including telomeres, centromeres, and REs.⁶⁵ Moreover, the interaction between Sirtuins (in particular SIRT1 and SIRT3) and p53 is a key regulatory mechanism in cellular stress responses, aging, and cancer.⁶⁶ SIRT1 and SIRT3 deacetylate and modulate the activity of p53, balancing the need for cell survival and the prevention of tumor formation (Figure 4).⁶⁶

Figure 4

Figure 4: The Role of NADPH and Sirtuins in Cellular Redox Homeostasis and DNA Methylation.

We hypothesize that the processes described above are fixed by a social evolutionary advantage, originating from the early development of eukaryotes as a collective adaptation for managing energy sources and their utilization through respiration. Within this framework, individuals' adaptive response to oxidative stress can result in the demethylation of REs, potentially reactivating their expression with several significant consequences. First, REs, such as transposons and retrotransposons, can insert themselves into new locations within the genome. This can disrupt gene function, create mutations, and cause chromosomal rearrangements, leading to genomic instability.⁶⁷ Second, reactivated REs can influence the expression of nearby genes, acting as alternative promoters, enhancers, or silencers, thereby altering the normal expression patterns of genes and potentially leading to modified cellular functions, aging, and diseases.⁶⁸ Finally, the reactivation of certain REs can be recognized by the cell as a viral infection, triggering an innate immune response, leading to inflammation and potentially contributing to autoimmune diseases and chronic inflammation.⁶⁹

The consequences mentioned can be understood within the framework of (epi)genetic and phenotypic adaptation. If the environmental load—whether macro or micro—exceeds the biological adaptation capabilities of the system (cells, tissues, organs), competing pathogenesis processes can initiate, leading to chronic diseases. For example, genomic instability and altered gene expression due to the reactivation of REs are associated with cancer development, as transposon insertions can activate oncogenes or inactivate tumor suppressor genes, contributing to tumorigenesis.²⁵ Moreover, the reactivation of REs has been linked to neurodegenerative diseases such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and frontotemporal dementia, where the insertional mutagenesis and subsequent cellular stress caused by REs can contribute to neuronal damage and degeneration.

Overall, the reactivation of REs is seen as a biological adaptation to a changing environment.⁷⁰ The balance between silencing and reactivation evolved as an "adapt or perish" principle. The individual dynamic adaptation capability is influenced by cellular senescence and aging processes, which decrease the baseline RE methylation.⁷¹ As biological age increases, under environmental stress the balance shifts from higher adaptation capacity to pathogenesis and death, serving as a form of biosocial adaptation in metazoans.

The aging effects of caloric intake exceeding the energy expenditure from physical activity support our hypothesis on the central role of metabolic energy balance in controlling epigenetic adaptation processes according to biological age. The individual accumulation of excess energy storage (as adiposity) is expected to pose a signal of net harm to the community. Thus, biosocial control mechanisms have evolved in populations facing environmental pressures regarding food resources. This condition, fixed in the context of the metabolism and lifestyles of Paleolithic hunter-gatherers, highlights the current necessity for continuous and sustained physical activity of humans. Physical activity provides an endogenous signal of social adaptation, thus preventing the promotion of cancer biology, which acts as an endoparasite accelerating the removal of unfit individuals. A similar balance is involved in all chronic diseases, as they represent coherent responses to unsuitable environments and behaviors, leading to accelerated aging and mortality processes.

Conclusions and Future Perspectives

Since the 1934 discovery that calorie restriction can extend lifespans by 50% in rats,⁷² the existence of species having negligible senescence and potentially immortal organisms (e.g. Hydra), led the interest in research on delaying senescence for preventing age-related diseases.⁷³ The subsequent evidence of moderated aerobic physical exercise in reducing chronic inflammation and promoting survival of humans, provided the basis of new clinical trials on the use of a fast-mimicking diet and physical exercise in cancer therapy as well as prevention.⁷⁴

From a metabolic perspective, the management of energy resources appears to drive adaptive biological health behaviors fixed by evolution at the community level, which may not always prioritize the survival of individuals. This condition should be accounted for in the future of health promotion and disease prevention programs. Given the social reflection of individual health, which is influenced by ancestral processes regulated at the epigenetic level, there is a pressing need for a new paradigm that prioritizes social and global biological sustainability as a primary driver. Physical activity is just one aspect of health promotion: emerging research also emphasizes the roles of well-being, happiness, and the aesthetic appreciation of visual arts and music. This broader perspective on health protection acknowledges happiness as a major biological fitness condition as a mandatory social responsibility.⁷⁵

The above perspective highlights the care attitude as a fundamental driver of both human biology and cultural evolution, suggesting a profound interconnection between social adaptivity and individual health outcomes. Within this framework, REs are suggested as key epigenetic transducers

of social adaptivity, bridging environmental interactions and social dynamics across various species. Future directions for our hypothesis will include an exploration of the contributions at the tissue and organ levels, specifically examining how the immune system mediates these processes. Through an eco-immunological perspective, the immune system is understood to orchestrate ontogenesis and regulate both acute and chronic inflammatory responses.

It should be stressed that the evidence sustained by this paper should be not framed in the reductionist perspective of the acceptance of diseases as positive selection factors. Moreover, no discriminating views justifying the existence of frailer biological groups and populations can be accepted. Instead, the efforts of humankind in the protection of health should be considered in the full social perspective of the worldwide community rather than individual biology.

This expanded understanding invites a reevaluation of the human role in global sustainability, emphasizing biological responsibility towards the protection of planetary life. By acknowledging the deep biological, cultural and social roots of health and disease, this approach fosters a view of human health that is inseparably linked to environmental stewardship and the well-being of all life forms.

Abbreviations

LTRs - Long Terminal Repeats
SINEs - Short Interspersed Nuclear Elements
LINEs - Long Interspersed Nuclear Elements
SAM - S-Adenosylmethionine
GSH - Glutathione
ROS - Reactive Oxygen Species
NADPH - Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate
SMT - Somatic Mutation Theory
SIRT - Sirtuins
AI - Artificial Intelligence

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

Elia Mario Biganzoli: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft.

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During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in order to help check and improve the English language and grammar. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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